

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer Review Report For:

Solaja, O. A., Oyedele. O. O., Olajugba, O. J., Abiodun, A. J., Edewor, O. J., Solaja, O. O., Kehinde, O. V and Akerelee, F. O. (2025). *SME performance and job creation in Sub-Saharan Africa: The role of digital innovation*. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(2), 2025. e2023-0553. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250201>

How to cite this Peer Review Report:

Solaja, O. A., Oyedele. O. O., Olajugba, O. J., Abiodun, A. J., Edewor, O. J., Solaja, O. O., Kehinde, O. V and Akerelee, F. O. (2025). Peer review report for: *SME performance and job creation in Sub-Saharan Africa: The role of digital innovation*. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(2), 2025. e2023-0553. *Zenodo*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14238807>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

Fred Peter , Landmark University College of Business and Social Sciences, Omu Aran, Nigeria

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity.

The third reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Fred Peter

Date review returned: 12-Jan-2024

Recommendation: Minor Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

ABSTRACT

While the abstract suggests that digital innovation is a valuable tool for poverty alleviation, it doesn't explicitly mention specific recommendations or strategies. Adding a sentence about potential policy or implementation recommendations would strengthen the conclusion.

INTRODUCTION

While integrating statistics and citations enhances the narrative's credibility, it tends to make the introduction less engaging for the reader. I recommend balancing the use of excessive citations in the introduction, as it can give it the appearance of a literature review.

METHODOLOGY

Provide a statement on the ethical considerations and measures taken to ensure participant confidentiality and privacy.

IMPLICATION:

Adding more specificity and details to certain recommendations could further enhance the practical applicability of the study's findings.

Authors' Responses

Chief Editor,

Revista de Administração de Empresas.

Dear Editor,

I write on behalf of myself and other co-authors to inform you that we have responded to editor and reviewers' comment.

Comment 1: *There are very lengthy paragraphs in some places, for example, the theoretical review and others, while in the introduction you may need to write in a way that engages your readers more with identifying the main gap of the study.*

Response 1: *We have address this and ensure the introduction is engaging enough.*

Comment 2: *At present, it is not exactly clear what the study aims to address and what is the main contributions of the study. Although the matter of poverty is widely studied in the existing literature, there is little evidence in your study about what is known of these previous studies and what remains to be known. Thus, the introduction section requires significant reworking. The introduction scantily integrates the theory adopted in the study. This is an area that should be addressed in the revised version of the work.*

Response 2: *We have been able to identify gap in previous studies that our study intends to focus on. And we have worked extensively on the introduction part of the study.*

Comment 3: *Also, the methodology needs significant reworking. Very little information is supplied on important aspects of the methods, for example, how were the instruments developed? Since the research included respondents from different countries attending a workshop, there is a need for further detail on how the research process was ensured. The baseline validity and reliability checks are included in tables but not discussed in the paper. There is no detail provided about the demographics of the respondents.*

Response 3: *We have reworked the methodology by including the source of our research instrument. We assured our respondent about the confidentiality of the study which we have reported in the study. The baseline validity and reliability are reported in the study but we gave it heading to show this in the manuscript. Also, the demographics of the respondents are now spelt out in the manuscript.*

Comment 4: *Also, there is no evidence in the main work of the relationship between digital innovation, job creation, and poverty alleviation. While table 4 shows evidence of these three variables, it is not understood how these variables relate and what possible implications could result. There is no hypothesis to reflect these relationships anywhere in the work.*

Response 4: *We have linked our variables together in this study and discussed in a way that will help to achieve the overall goal of the study.*

Thank you for your efforts and comment on our Manuscript.

Thank you and God Bless you.

Authors

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Fred Peter

Date review returned: 26-Jun-2024

Recommendation: Minor Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

No conflict of interest

Comments to the Author

Following a review of the manuscript titled “ALLEVIATING POVERTY IN SUB-SAHARA AFRICA: DIGITAL INNOVATION DIFFUSION THROUGH SMEs,” here are some of my thoughts:

Title and abstract:

The title is simple and descriptive, effectively conveying the study’s major point.

The abstract is succinct and effectively conveys the research. However, the author should consider mentioning particular findings or implications to provide a more thorough summary.

Introduction:

The introduction gives a strong background on poverty in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and the significance of digital innovation.

However, the research gap and the significance of the study needs to be improved.

Literature Review

The literature assessment is comprehensive, encompassing many elements of digital innovation and poverty. The author should ensure that all sources are properly cited and that recent studies are used to back up arguments.

Methodology:

SEM and the SEMinR package in R are suitable for data analysis.

Clearly explain the rationale for picking 655 SMEs,

Results and Discussion:

The results section should clearly convey the findings.

In the discussion, make careful to tie the findings back to the literature and theoretical framework, emphasizing the study's contributions.

Conclusion:

The conclusion summarizes the key points well but could be enhanced by discussing the practical implications and potential policy recommendations.